

DEVELOPMENT AND MODERNIZATIONS IN UZBEK MUSEUMS: FINANCIAL, TECHNICAL, AND COLLABORATIVE IMPROVEMENTS

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Abstract. *Museums are one of the main and important places to learn about art, culture and history. However, nowadays many people are getting bored because of uninspiring atmosphere and lack of exhibitions and artefacts. So, there are some methods available to increase public interest on museums, such as focusing on museums budget and rise financial support to ensure museums' financial independence. Another strategy is using advanced technologies to create unforgettable environment for visitors and make their visit more interesting. And to attract young audience there should be special partnership between museums and academic institutions. In overall, implementing these steps will be helpful to expand museums' role in Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *financial support, renting out collections, augmented reality, virtual reality, educational projects.*

Аннотация. *В наши дни музеи являются важными местами для изучения искусства, истории и культуры. Однако из-за однообразной атмосферы и ограниченности коллекций музеи стали казаться скучными для многих посетителей. Тем не менее, интерес населения к музеям можно повысить за счёт финансовой поддержки и обеспечения их финансовой независимости. Другой эффективной стратегией является расширение использования современных технологий в музеях, что поможет создать незабываемую и увлекательную атмосферу для посетителей. Кроме того, чтобы привлечь больше молодёжи, музеям следует активнее сотрудничать со школами и другими образовательными учреждениями. В целом, реализация вышеуказанных проектов будет способствовать расширению роли музеев в Узбекистане.*

Ключевые слова: *финансовая поддержка, аренда коллекций, виртуальная реальность, образовательные проекты.*

Annotatsiya. *Bugungi kunda muzeylar san'at, tarix va madaniyatlarni o'rganish uchun muhim joylardan biri hisoblanadi. Ammo, ayni kunlarda muzeylardagi zeriktiruvchi muhit va kolleksiyalarning kamligi tufayli muzeylar ko'pchilik tashrif buyuruvchilar uchun zerikarli bo'lib qolgan. Biroq muzeylarga moliyaviy tomondan ko'maklashish va ularning moliyaviy mustaqilligini ta'minlash orqali aholining muzeylarga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshirish mumkin. Yana bir boshqa strategiya esa - muzeylarda rivojlangan texnologiyalarning o'rnini kengaytirish va shu orqali tashrif buyuruvchilarga unutilmas va qiziqarli muhit yaratib berishdir. Va shu bilan bir qatorda yoshlarni ko'proq muzeylarga jalb qilish maqsadida muzeylar maktablar va boshqa o'quv muassasalari bilan hamkorlik olib borilishi lozim.*

Umumiy qilib aytganda yuqoridagi loyihalarni amalga oshirish O'zbekistonda muzeylarning rolini yanada kengaytirish uchun foydali bo'ladi.

***Kalit so'zlar:** moliyaviy yordam, kolleksiyalarni ijaraga berib yuborish, virtual reallik, o'quv loyihalari.*

Introduction

In recent years, learning history and cultural heritage are one of the favourable activities of people and that is why many of them prefer to visit museum. But, there are some complains that museums are not interesting places to spend time, because there are almost no updates and advanced technologies to attract wider audience, it is because there is not enough sponsorship to cover all expenses of museums. So, government and stakeholders should increase the amount of financial support for uzbek museums for new artefacts and buying advanced technologies to attract more audience and museums should develop partnership with educational centers to increase public interest on museums. This following article will focus on some methods such as, investing more money to buy new collections, advanced technologies that can increase public interest and working with educational institutions to attract young visitors, by giving some examples and explanation

Discussion: Importance of Financial Support for Museums

Increasing the amount of fundings for museums can help to purchase for more artefacts and prevent them from being sold to cover the expenses of museums. Museums' budget usually relies on admission revenues and donations. But these sources are not enough to cover all the expenses or buying new stuffs especially famous artefacts that can attract more people. In recent years, many museums were closed because of not enough financial support. In 2004, Burg and other researchers mentioned one of their article called “Raising private investment funds for museums”: “The fund could put the part of its resources that is not initially used into short-term deposits”. That means some museums rent out their collection to handle all the financial issues just for while. So, after renting out they might lose more money than they receive, “The paintings owned by a fund can be exhibited in prestigious museums for a number of years” (Burg et al., 2004). There are some other researchers who mentioned the role of financial support in museums, as Coslor mentioned one of her research “The recent financial crisis and attendant endowment declines have increased pressure on some museums to find cost savings”(2009). As written above, facing to financial shortages is the weakest side of the museums and that is why governmental support, donations and charities play an important role in running museums. Nowadays, government pays less attention to museums, and sometimes only donations and admission revenues are not enough to paying all the costs. That is why I decided to conduct a survey that asks public's opinion about what should be the main source for financial support in museums.

Figure 1

Financial support in museums

What do you think, which one is the best to get financial support for museums?

25 ОТВЕТОВ

Note. As shown in this chart above, 68% of respondents think that government should be the main source in museums for economic support, only 24% and 8% of them support other ways to earn money for museums, especially donations and selling the cultural items from the museums.

As revealed from provided information, government plays crucial role to run museums and to maintain public attendance in museums.

Solutions: Using Advanced Technology in Museums Field

Chinese advanced technologies are the best example to digitalize museums and help visitors to feel the real historical atmosphere. It is widely recognized that China is well-known for its technological development and chinese government was the first that started using digital tools in museums field. In 21st century technology is an important part of our life and therefore they must be applied across every field, even in museums, as Ding mentioned “We live in a digital age and people are more than accustomed to holding up their mobile devices to take pictures, therefore holding up their devices to scan an AR object more easily fits into the museum experience” (2017), looking at some other researchers studies, Alelis wrote one of her article that was about the usage of 3D technologies in museums field, she mentioned “Museums are increasingly offering new methods of engaging and educating visitors through the use of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) systems” (n.d). That means, nowadays only technology can help to increase public interest for museums, it’s because these days people are addicted to the gadgets and that is why many researchers are suggesting advanced technologies in museums. As Bender mentioned, “Both reality technologies [virtual reality and augmented reality] place the central focus on user experience and provide greater interactivity and engagement” (2017). Augmented reality is the type of technology that can make museums more interesting by adding digital features to exhibitions, while virtual reality creates entirely AI-powered atmosphere that can show real spirit of history to the visitors. “Museums and cultural institutions have been exploring the concept of reality as a way to make art and art history more engaging” (Bender, 2017). For example, Chinese government uses such specific technologies to engage more visitors to museums, and by using those Chinese methods in uzbek museums it will be easier to attract more visitors, even young generations, because “technology offers ways to incorporate greater interactivity and engagement in the classroom, and has changed how teachers and students interact in the classroom” (Blasco-Arcas, 2013), and with new technological era even young audience may get interest on visiting museums. So, applying these technologies in uzbek museums offers

changes and more interest in museums. In the following paragraph we will focus on other method for increasing public interest on museums.

Special Methods to Increase Public Interest in Museums

Collaborating with trainers and teachers in educational centers and schools, and training them helps them to encourage learners to visit museums more often. As written above using technologies in museums field is one of the ways to spark interest among young visitors, but this method is not enough to encourage more visitors. That is why museums should collaborate with educational institutions such as schools, colleges and educational centers. Such educational programs can be implemented whether in schools or museums. In both sectors its important to have qualified teachers and trainers and training them with the right and new methods, so they can help to encourage youngsters to visit museums and make those young audience more interested in museums field. As Tzibazi mentioned in one of his studies “if a learning partnership between ITT [ITT – initial training teachers is the specific training program for te teachers] and museums could unfold within this perspective more space could be given for imaginative, authentic choices and unexpected learning encounters” (2011), and with these words he specifies the importance of training for teachers. For instance, teachers and trainers should learn to create interesting atmosphere, instead of teaching inside the boring classrooms all the time and in this case museums play crucial role there. “It is believed that if student teachers deepen their understanding about the value of teaching outside the classroom then they will embed the use of museums into their , future professional practice” (Tzibazi, 2011). So, it is evident from that museums are not places to visit and watch the exhibitions, they are also important to feel the real atmosphere of art and history. Actually, “looking at the history, it can be seen that the role of museums was not teaching about the artifacts in the boring ways, but they needed to help visitors to feel the atmosphere by generating stimulating cultural and historical experience” (Tzibazi, 2011). Applying special programs only at schools might not be successful enough, therefore from the recent years with the help of trainers museums started different projects that can boost visitors interest on museums, as Lechner said in her article, “Some art museums even created educational programs before their institutions were initially built or their collections were completed” (2018). So, with all information above, I wanted to explain the role of museums in society, museums are not just boring places they are actually real history and culture.

Conclusion

As a conclusion, it is important to mention that museums play special role to learn history and so maintenance their value in our society is important. For that, government should pay more attention to cover museums weaknesses, give enough financial support to equip museums with advanced technologies and to teach how to use such modern equipment in museums field there must be special master-classes for museum workers, and another practical recommendation is setting up specialized programs with unique teaching methods between trainers and learners in museums field, so it can help to attract more learners in that field. Generally, applying all these techniques is important to develop the role of museums in our life, because museums are special places that can keep our history, culture and traditions alive.

REFERENCES

1. Alesis, G., Bobrowicz, A., & Ang, C. S. (n.d.). Comparison of engagement and emotional responses of older and younger adults interacting with 3D cultural heritage artefacts on personal devices. Canterbury.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/277554794_Comparison_of_engagement_and_emotional_responses_of_older_and_younger_adults_interacting_with_3D_cultural_heritage_artefacts_on_personal_devices
2. Coslor, E. (2009). Art investment collections: A new model for museum finance? *University of Chicaco, Department of Sociology*.
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2359260
3. Der Burg, T., Dolfsma & W., Wilderom, W. (2004). Raising private investment funds for museums. *International Journal of Arts Management*, 6(3), 50-59
<https://research.utwente.nl/en/publications/4aa80fc4-c79a-43e9-835f-a06a2e34d6e9>
4. Ding, M. (2017). Augmented reality in museums. *Arts Management & Technology Laboratory*. p.1-12. <https://www.museumnext.com/article/how-museums-are-using-augmented-reality/>
5. Lechner, N. (2018). Engaging, educating, and evolving: A case study of three art museums in Arizona (thesis). *Graduate Supervisory Committie, Arizona*.
<https://hdl.handle.net/2286/R.I.49104>
6. Tzibazi, V. (2011). Rethinking the learning partnership between museums and initial teacher training. *International Journal for Cross-Disciplinary Subjects in Education*, 2(2), 407–413.